

TERRIFIC

BIOBASED FLAGSHIP PACKAGING SOLUTIONS

Next generation circular biobased flagship packaging: a catalyst for the green transition

Grant Agreement n 101157635

HORIZON-JU-CBE-2023

D1.9 Project Website

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List of Acronyms

MIG	MULTIACTOR INTEREST GROUP
WPs	Work Packages

Disclaimer

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Publishable summary

The TERRIFIC project website has been designed and developed to serve as a key source for up-to-date information on project partners, activities, and objectives. It provides comprehensive details about the project's main outcomes and results, and functions as a communication hub for the target audience. Additionally, the website is designed to foster a community of active members thanks to the integration with the project's social media profiles and newsletter.

Starting on 30 September 2024, the project website can be accessed at the following address <https://terrificproject.eu/>.

The content of the website is updated regularly following partners' and users' suggestions and needs that may arise as the project is implemented. If needed, also the website structure could be upgraded (e.g. adding sub-sections or interactive links).

To ensure project long-term sustainability, the project website will remain operational, maintained, and updated during the entire duration of the project and at least 1 year after the project end, and will remain operational at least 5 years after the project end.

The information contained in the TERRIFIC website is structured in 6 sections, as follows:

1. *HOME*: hosts a general video, a scheme illustrating the project concept and a short description of the project, as well as the main news related to the Project implementation.
2. *THE PROJECT*: presents the objectives and the structure (WPs) of the Project.
3. *FLAGSHIP SOLUTIONS*: contains information on the 8 bio-based circular flagship packaging solutions which will be demonstrated during the Project.
4. *CONSORTIUM*: contains a map and the list of the Project partners with a short description. It also contains information related to the Multi-Actor Interest Group.
5. *MEDIA*: gives to possibility to subscribe to project's newsletter, and it is then structured in four sub-sections:
 - a. News: news regarding the project activities and implementation.
 - b. Documents: public project deliverables and documents of interest.
 - c. Gallery: photos and videos of project meetings and activities.
 - d. Press Kit.
6. *CONTACTS*: allows users to contact TERRIFIC project for requests and to follow the Project on three different social media: X, LinkedIn, Youtube.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The development and the structure of the project website is part of the development of effective communication online channels (website, social media, newsletter, promotional campaigns) for the project target audiences, increasing project visibility, providing the latest news on achievements and results, and supporting the engagement of stakeholders.

In this context, the TERRIFIC project website has been designed and created to:

- Being a primary point of reference for up-to-date information on project partners, activities, and results.
- Providing an intuitive graphic interface for users to navigate the website and find relevant information.
- Storing all the public reports (including public deliverables) and other public documents produced within the TERRIFIC Project.
- Hosting the TERRIFIC outreach channels (i.e. social profiles and newsletter). Dedicated links to the TERRIFIC social profiles are available on the project website and is possible to subscribe to the TERRIFIC project newsletters via the project website.
- Stimulating the dialogue between stakeholders by promoting different project events.
- Ensuring the project's long-term impact by remaining updated at least 1 year after the project's end and operational at least 5 years after the project's end.

The project website is compliant with the requirements and obligations related to the Visibility of the EU funding & obligation to use the EU emblem and CBE JU logos (Art. 17 GA).

2 ACCESS, HOSTING AND MAINTENANCE

2.1 Public Access to the Website

The project website is accessible by the public starting from 30 September 2024 at the following address: <https://terrificproject.eu/>. The website is available in English.

2.2 Updates

SPRING is responsible for the managing and updating of the website. The website is updated regularly, on a monthly basis or whenever deemed necessary, in the content (e.g. a new event is planned, a new public deliverable is produced, a new knowledge exchange is organized, etc..) and, if needed, in its structure (e.g. adding sub-sections) following partners' and users' suggestions and needs that may arise as the project is implemented, and in coordination with Novamont (as Project coordinator). Main updates of the website after its first release are already planned in view of enhancing usability and ensure good communication and dissemination. Details of the upcoming updates are reported in the following section of this document.

2.3 Analytics

TERRIFIC website allows to SPRING to monitor the activities and collect the number of unique visitors, that will be used to verify the timely achievement of the KPIs and, if necessary, to implement additional actions to maximize the visibility of the website.

3 STRUCTURE OF THE WEBSITE

The project website is composed of 6 sections which are described in detail in this paragraph. Each section has been developed to be easily comprehensible also using tablets and/or smartphones: in this case the schemes and images has been re-edited to be more readable.

3.1 HOME

The “HOME” main section contains a scheme of the overall concept of TERRIFIC project and a short description (Figure 1).

- HOME
- THE PROJECT
- FLAGSHIP SOLUTIONS
- CONSORTIUM
- MEDIA
- CONTACTS

TERRIFIC - NEXT GENERATION CIRCULAR BIODEBASED FLAGSHIP PACKAGING: A CATALYST FOR THE GREEN TRANSITION

The TERRIFIC project aims to reform the packaging sector with bio-based solutions that enhance performance, circularity, and resource efficiency throughout the entire value chain, boosting the development of a bioeconomy model able to decouple the European development from the use of resources. TERRIFIC flagship biobased products showcase the potential of bioeconomy to drive ecological transition, circularity, and to reach important goals in pollution prevention and decarbonization.

TERRIFIC will demonstrate a first-of-its-kind multipurpose biorefinery to produce bio-based materials starting from sustainable, EU-sourced feedstocks, and will implement a platform of novel biomaterials responding to packaging sector needs in terms of thermal and barrier properties, while meeting technical and durability requirements. Eight flagship packaging products will be developed and validated across the entire value chain, considering different end-of-life scenarios and proposing secondary value chains based on recycled biopolymer materials for non-food packaging solutions.

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- THE PROJECT
- MEDIA
- CONTACTS
- FLAGSHIP SOLUTION
- CONSORTIUM

Figure 1: screenshot of TERRIFIC project website homepage

The homepage footer presents the logo, the links to the other website pages, and the emblems of CBE-JU, BIC, EU flag and the funding disclaimer comprehensive of the grant agreement number.

A first update of the homepage will be implemented by inserting the first video describing the project, and during the lifespan of the project the homepage will also show direct updates and links to the most recent news regarding project implementation, events, and outputs.

3.2 THE PROJECT

This section presents the project objectives and the project structure. The WPs are presented as general scheme to better understand activities and interlinks among WPs, followed by a short description of each WP (Figure 2).

A first update of “The Project” page will make the page more interactive: the text parts will be removed, and they will appear when moving the pointer on the different figures and diagrams.

3.3 FLAGSHIP SOLUTIONS

This section aims at presenting the biobased circular packaging solutions demonstrated in the TERRIFIC project, with a general introduction followed by a focus on each single bioproduct (Figure 3).

Figure 3: selected screenshot of the “Flagship Solutions” webpage

The “Flagship Solutions” webpage will be updated during the implementation of the project with links to factsheets dedicated to each specific solution.

3.4 CONSORTIUM

This page presents the consortium, with a map showing the partners and related EU Countries participating in the project, followed by a short description of each participating partner (logo and short description). Moreover, a scheme and short description of the Multi-actor Interest Group (MIG) is presented.

Figure 4: selected screenshots of the "Consortium" webpage

The "consortium" page first update will allow to visualize the partners' descriptions just moving the cursor on the map and will add a direct link to the partners' websites.

During the lifespan of the project updates to the composition and activities of the MIG will be uploaded.

3.5 MEDIA

This section is divided in four sub-sections (Figure 5):

- *News*: here the news about the project will be published, allowing to share information about project meetings, events, workshops, etc.
- *Documents*: here the public deliverables, as well as every public informative or document will be available for download
- *Gallery*: a section dedicated to the sharing of images and photos of project meetings, events, prototypes obtained, etc.

- *Press Kit*: gives the possibility to download the project logo and the first press release of TERRIFIC. The press kit material will be updated during the duration of the project, with project presentation and further press releases.

Figure 5: Screenshot of the “Media” webpage

Shifting from one sub-section to another is highlighted by a green leaf that recalls the leaves of the project logo.

The media page also presents a mask for subscribing to the project newsletter, so that interest audience can know more about the project and stay updated on TERRIFIC activities and events. The user is asked to fill a form requiring full name, company, role, country, email address, to read and agree to the terms and conditions of Privacy Policy, and then to press “SIGN UP”.

The media page will be updated regularly, whenever deemed necessary, following the availability of project news, events, publications, and other communication and dissemination materials.

3.6 CONTACTS

In this page is possible for the users to send a short message for inquiries about the project, through a user-friendly interface. The page reports also the logo and name of the coordinator

(Novamont) and the links to the social media channels, as well as the newsletter subscription mask. Information provided by the user will be managed according to updated Privacy Policy.

Figure 6: Screenshot of the “Contacts” webpage